

THE CONCEPT OF POSSIBILISM IN GEOGRAPHY

Xatamova Qumrixon¹, Vahobjonov Akbarjon²

¹Fergana State University, Faculty of Natural Sciences, 2nd year student of geography

²Fergana State University, Faculty of Natural Sciences, 2nd year student of geography

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5448983>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 25th August 2021

Accepted: 30th August 2021

Online: 05th September 2021

KEY WORDS

*Communication,
geopolitics, admiral,
geopolitics, autarky*

ABSTRACT

This article presents theories about the origin of the concept of possibilism and who introduced it to science.

The history of opinions expressed about political organizations (states) dates back to ancient times (Herodotus, Thucydides, Strabo, Polybius). The new period provided evidence of the impact of geographical (continental, island or coastal states, their territory, length of coastal borders, communication capabilities in the state, landscape and climate) and the impact of demographic factors on the socio-political life of peoples (G. Gerder, E. Reklyu, and b). As a result of such research, in the second half of the XIX century - the beginning of the XX century, geopolitics emerged as a separate science from the depths of the comprehensive socio-political sciences. It should be noted that the term classical geopolitics refers to the views of researchers who have created since that time and influenced the historical development of geopolitics to one degree or another. Among them are the German

scientist F. Ratzel (1844-1904), the Swedish statesman R. Chellen (1864-1922), the American admiral A. Mexen (1840-1914), the English geographer H. McKinder (1861-1947), the German scientist K. Haushofer (1869-1946), the American (originally Dutch) N. Spikman (1893-1943) and the Russian economist PNSavisky (1895 - 1968) are the most famous classical geopolitical scientists.

Although Friedrich Ratzel did not use the term "geopolitics" in his works, he was one of the first to be called the father of the science of geopolitics because he thought in a geopolitical style. He discusses political geography in his works, and his main scholarly work on the subject is also called political geography (1897). He stressed that the interests of any nation lie on the ground. Therefore, certain areas on the ground are the main means of indicating the movement of history. States are

reflected on the ground in the form of specific territories. The earth can be eternal, the regions (states) will change. The "example of states is a living organism" whose core is basically the ground that connects them to each other.

According to F. Ratzel, the formation of the "state - a living organism" is due to the assimilation of small political structures. Its boundaries serve as the periphery of the "state - living organism". Emphasizing that the tendency of states to grow is hidden in a natural being, F. Ratzel considers interstate relations only on the basis of confrontation, conflict or military conflict. In the practice of such relations, "the weakening or further weakening of the state is the result of its spatial perception."

2. The concepts of Rudolf Chellen and Friedrich Naumann

R.Chellen's acquaintance with F.Ratzel: made a sharp turn in his work. Although R.Chellen could not find a professional geographer, under the influence of F.Ratzel he was able to put forward new ideas in geopolitics. That is why he considered F. Ratzel as his mentor. R. Chellen viewed geopolitics as an important part of political science. His works "Great Powers: Essays on Modern Big Politics" (1914), "The State as an Important Form of Life" (1916), "Fundamentals of Political Order" (1920) form the basis of the scientist's work.

Natural and geographical features - the geographical location of the country, access to international trade, the world of fauna and flora, climate, etc.

By state economy, R. Chellen refers to the factors that allow the state to sustain itself based on its existing capabilities - natural resource resources, market structures and other similar factors, and the

extent to which they are integrated with the world economy. In economic relations, R. Chellen advocates autarky - the achievement of a national economic system based on the state's self-supply to the population of the country without importing the necessary things.

The people are the national-ethnic groups living in this country. However, R. Chellen evaluates the people living in the state on the basis of cultural, ethnic and demographic relations. The scientist used the term "biopolitics" in his study. According to him, biopolitics studies the way of life of peoples, which creates the "criteria of society: mind, heart and order."

By form of government, R. Chellen does not mean the system of government. It refers to the form of government, on the one hand, freedom of conscience in the state, freedom of thought, freedom of assembly, etc., on the other hand, the obligation to pay taxes to the state, military service obligations, schooling, and so on. . Because the fact that these factors are reflected in practice shows how powerful that form of government is. R. Chellen was the first in geopolitics to put forward the theory of building a great state (power) in his book "Modern Great Powers". In his view, great states (powers) should be the subject of geopolitical processes, as well as logically form the basis of the subject of geopolitics. The researcher divides the great states (powers) into two, i.e. the international powers and the great powers. He included Britain, the United States, Russia and Germany in the ranks of international forces before World War I. As great powers, Japan, France, Italy and the Austro-Hungarian Empire were built.

Given that Germany was located in the "heart of Europe", F. Ratzel proposed in

1901 to establish a great German economic union between the German states. Thus, F. Ratzel's theoretical ideas about the central region, with the views of R. Chellen and F. Naumann, gradually began to arouse public interest.

Karl Haushofer is one of the brightest representatives of the German school of geopolitics. From 1924, for 20 years, he published the journal *Geopolitics*, which was of international importance.

There are various opposing views among geopolitical scholars on the work of K. Haushofer, including his attitude to the ideology of German nationalism. In our view, his attitude towards Nazism was of a complex nature, with one scale of his views reflecting the views of the National-Socialists, while at times reflecting a radical attitude. K. Haushofer was not a representative of the Nazi ideology. Perhaps it would be more accurate to say that it was K. Haushofer's views that influenced the formation of the geostrategic programs of the German political elite at that time. For example, let us compare the views of K. Haushofer with the practical political actions of the German ruling circles in the first half of the XX century to establish a new order in the world. If an in-depth analysis of the geopolitical concepts put forward by K. Haushofer, H. McKinder, J. Fergriv, A. Mexen and other scientists and politicians, the dominance of "coastal" or "outer crescent" states in Eurasia While the ruling Nazis advocated the need for a "continental bloc" between Berlin, Moscow, and Tokyo in order to avoid internal conflicts in Hartland, Moscow's ideological position was that Taking advantage of their inability to link Tokyo, they saw the need to create a New Order in collaboration with Rome, which was ideologically closer to them.

K. Haushofer calls the German people and the historical roots of their culture to Asia-Eurasia and interprets German culture as a garb of the whole Eurasian culture. This is probably why the British also called the Germans "Huns" during World War II. This name was very popular among the representatives of the Haushofer school of geopolitics.

The basic idea of geopolitics is that man's dependence on the geographical environment becomes more and more apparent as he moves away from the individual to the group of people. Therefore, despite the existence of a certain ideological foundation, geopolitics has not been able to become a real ideology, or rather a mass ideology. Its conclusions and methods, the subject of research, and its basic rules may be relevant only to the social strata dealing with the enormous problems of strategic planning, the assessment of universal laws of a social and historical nature. Because geopolitical space is manifested on a very large scale, geopolitics is also aimed at social groups related to the generalized realities of states, peoples, and so on.

The basic principle of geopolitics is to express the rigidity of the fundamental dualism expressed in the geographical structure of the Earth's surface and the division of civilizations into historical types. This dualism is manifested in the contrast between "tellurocracy" ("land power") and "thalassocracy" ("naval power"). The essence of such a confrontation is clearly seen in the example of the interaction of the famous commercial civilization Carthage (Athens) and the military-authoritarian civilization Sparta (Rome) in the history of antiquity. In other words, it is a contradiction between democracy and ideocracy based on a liberal idea. From the very beginning, this

contradiction has the character of the opposite of the poles that make it up, and varies according to the requirements of the period.

Thus, the whole of social history consists of processes that take place around two elements, namely, "water" ("liquid", "reader") and "land" ("solid", "permanent"). Tellurocracy is characterized by the stability of space and the stability of its main features. At the civilizational level, tellurocracy is manifested in sedentary, conservatism, strict legal norms to which large associations of people, peoples, states, empires are subordinated. The rigidity of the land also has a serious impact on the cultural life of the peoples, including the stability of social traditions and the stability of moral rules formed under the influence of this factor. The peoples of the continent, that is, the interior of Eurasia, have a foreign spirit of individualism, which has long been characterized by a social psyche and a hierarchical system.

It should be noted that geopolitical laws are especially useful in political history, the history of diplomacy, and strategic

planning and analysis. This science has points of intersection with many disciplines such as sociology, political science, ethnology, military strategy, diplomacy, history of religion. Some experts have suggested the introduction of a science called "geoeconomics", given that in many cases this science is inextricably linked with the economy.

In his book *The Influence of the Navy on History (1660 - 1783)*, A. Mexen emphasizes the greatness of the naval factor in the history of civilization. The degree to which a nation uses the sea in its own life shows how well-off those nations are and whether or not they have the power to influence others. Among such states, he firmly cited England as an example - he was the ruler of the world's major seas until the early twentieth century. He pitted the United States against Britain to put his theoretical predictions into practice, insisting that the U.S. would first subjugate the Philippine Islands in the Pacific to become a naval hub. After all, A. Mexen sees the Philippines as a strategic region in which the U.S. is becoming a naval hub and should occupy it.

References:

1. Jalilov A., Helford Mackinder's geopolitical views // *Society and Management*, 2006, No. 2.
2. *Political science in Uzbekistan*. - T.: Sharq, 2002.
3. Huntington S. *Stolknovenie tsivilizatsiy i pereustroystvo mirovogo poryadka* // «Polis», 1994, № 1.
4. Vasilenko I.A. *Geopolitics*. - M. Logos, 2003.
5. Gadjiev K.S. *Introduction to geopolitics*. Izd 2, dop. and pererab. M., 2001.